

**RELATIONS BETWEEN CHEMICAL ACTIVITY AND ABSORPTION IN THE
ULTRAVIOLET OF CERTAIN ORGANIC MOLECULES. PART VIII.
ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF MONOCHLORO DERIVATIVES
OF THE AMIDES OF ACETOACETIC ACID**

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Changes in light absorption have been studied by replacing hydrogen atoms of the central methylene group of the following compounds:

(1) Monochloroacetoacetanilide, (2) monochloroacetoacet-1:3:4-xylylamide, (3) monochloroacetoacet- α -naphthylamide.

Comparing the curves of these chloro derivatives with those of the non-substituted amides, it is found that in the case of the chloro-derivatives: (i) the degree of light absorption increases, (ii) the curves are shifted towards the visible.

In order to study the change taking place in light absorption when the structure of the amides is altered by replacing the hydrogen atoms of the central methylene group, the following compounds have been studied:

1. Monochloroacetoacetanilide.
2. Monochloroacetoacet-1:3:4-xylylamide.
3. Monochloroacetoacet- α -naphthylamide.

The difference between the structure of the amides and their chloro derivatives is as under

The methylene group (-CH₂-), situated between two carbonyl groups, has been transformed into -CHCl-. It was expected that such a transformation of the group should

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

bring about a change in light absorption. This expectation has been amply realised in the present study.

On Fig. 1 have been traced the curves of :—

- (1) Acetoacetanilide.
- (2) Acetoacet-1:3:4-xylylamide.
- (3) Monochloroacetoacet-1:3:4-xylylamide.
- (4) Monochloroacetoacetanilide.

On comparison of the curves of the non-substituted amides with those of the respective chloro-amides it will be seen that, in the case of chlorocompounds (i) the degree of light absorption increases, and (ii) the curves are shifted towards the visible region. Similar observations have also been made by Mme. Ramart, Naik and Mehta (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 16, 421).

In Fig. 2 are traced the curves of

- (1) Acetoacet-*a*-naphthylamide.
- (2) Monochloroacetoacet-*a*-naphthylamide.

Observations similar to those made above can be made in this case too.

From all these it can be said that the sum-total effect of the transformation of $-\text{CH}_3$ to $-\text{CHCl}$ group is to increase the degree of absorption, as also to shift the curves towards the visible. The peculiar position and nature of each curve depend upon the position and heaviness of radicals attached to the carbonyl groups. It may also be pointed out that generally *w.e* heavier the radical, the greater the shifting of the absorption curves towards the visible. The absorption curves of tolylamides illustrate the difference in the position of the curve due to the proximity or distance of the methyl group, to or from the original amino group.

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